

Pride and rights

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In June, LBGTI people publicly express their demands for respect and identity. They walk with joy, with less fear and expectation, so that others see them and recognize them as equals in the protection and defence of their intrinsic rights, as human beings.

The Universal Declaration of 1948 states that everyone deserves minimum protections that should be provided by states, regardless of race, sex or ideology, yet this is not the case for thousands of people. The struggles to live in dignity continue. It is still difficult to be on an equal footing for having a different skin colour, living outside the cities, being born in a country in the global south, being a woman or thinking differently.

Political and religious leaders "open doors" for gays and lesbians, but more than concession would be "giving back" the freedom of expression that those marginalised from their families and communities because of sexual preferences should always have had.

Democracy theorists claim that tolerance and participation of minorities are among the foundations of the pluralistic model of society that governs many nations in the 21st century, but is it true when it is condemned, banished and ignored because of dress, hairstyles, dances or idioms?

Perhaps one of the keys to authentic citizenship lies in celebrating all words, forms, colours, and creeds. May the coming years be years of thousands of different, diverse, lively young people, who proclaim their identities from the recognition of others, without following models designed by the violence exercised by those who have power.